

D4.6 Complete prototypes of wearable strap and sock

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About ThrombUS+

Deep vein thrombosis (DVT) is the formation of a blood clot within the deep veins, most commonly those of the lower limbs, causing obstruction of blood flow. In 50% of people with DVT, the clot eventually breaks off and travels to the lung to cause pulmonary embolism. Clinical assessment of DVT is notoriously unreliable because up to 2/3 of DVT episodes are clinically silent and patients are symptom free even when pulmonary embolism has developed. Early diagnosis of DVT is crucial and despite the progress made in ultrasound imaging and plethysmography techniques, there is a need for new methods to enable continuous monitoring DVT diagnosis at the point of care.

ThrombUS+ brings together an interdisciplinary team of industrial, technology, regulatory, social science and clinical trial experts to develop a novel wearable diagnostic device for point-of-care, operator free, continuous monitoring in patients with high DVT risk. The device will combine autonomous, AI driven DVT detection based on a novel wearable ultrasound hardware, impedance plethysmography and light reflection rheography for immediate detection of blood clot formation in the lower limb. Activity and other physiological measurements will be used to provide a continuous assessment of DVT risk and support DVT prevention via serious gaming. The aggregated data will drive an intelligence decision support unit that will provide accurate monitoring and alerts. Extended reality will be used to guide experts to design exercises and patients to use the device optimally.

ThrombUS+ is intended for use by postoperative patients in the ward, during long surgical operations, cancer patients or otherwise bedridden patients at home or in care units, and women during pregnancy and postpartum. ThrombUS+ will use big data sets for AI training collected in the project via 3 large scale clinical studies and will validate the outcome in the clinical setting via 1 early feasibility study and 1 multi-center clinical trial.

Deliverable D4.6 Description

Deliverable D4.6 involves the manufacturing of wearable prototypes for the ThrombUS+ system. Sufficient quantities of each component will be produced to create at least 10 complete ThrombUS+ systems. This document serves as the report on the production of these prototypes. The report and the prototypes are outcomes of Task 4.6, where each partner is responsible for producing their respective wearable, hardware and software. This task is led by ComfTech and involves TAU, medis and KTU.

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Terms and Definitions

Term	Definition
CDUS	Compression Duplex Ultrasonography
CHI	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Central Hub & Intelligence Module
CSW	Identifier for ThrombUS+ C-shell type Semirigid Wearable
DVT	Deep Vein Thrombosis
EAC	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Electronic Actuator Controller
EC	European Commission
EIM	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Electrical Impedance Module
EIP	Electrical Impedance Plethysmography
GUI	Graphical User Interface
EU	European Union
HADEA	European Health and Digital Executive Agency
IMU	Inertial Measurement Unit
LAM	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Limb Activity Module
LRM	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Light Rheography Module
LRR	Light Reflection Rheography
PPG	Photoplethysmography
RUC(s)	Reference Use Case(s)
SDK	Software Development Kit
SoftAP	Software-enabled Access Point
TL	Task Leader
USM	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Ultrasound Monitoring Module
VOP	Venous Occlusion Plethysmography
WAM	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Wearable Actuator Module
WSN	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Wearable Sensors Network
WTC	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Wearable Thigh Cuff
WTE	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Wearable Tetrapolar Electrode
WUSD	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Wearable Ultrasound Device
XGM	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Extended Reality and Serious Gaming Module
XR	Extended Reality

Executive Summary

This deliverable reports the result of Task 4.6, which concerned the manufacturing of the final wearable prototypes of the ThrombUS+ system. The main outcome of this task is the production of twelve (12) complete wearable prototype sets, comprising the components of the wearable Sensors Network (WSN) and the wearable part of the Wearable Ultrasound Device (WUSD).

Within work package 4 (WP4), the task focused on the development and manufacturing of wearable sensors, hardware and software required for implementing methods for deep vein thrombosis (DVT) monitoring and prevention. These methods include the electrical impedance plethysmography, light reflection rheography and lower limb activity monitoring. The resulting prototypes described in this deliverable constitute the final version of the Wearable Sensors Network subsystem and will be integrated into the overall ThrombUS+ system.

In parallel, wearable components related to the Wearable ultrasound Device were finalized in coordination with Task 3.6. Together, the subsystem forms a complete multi-modal wearable system for continuous and operator-independent DVT monitoring.

Out of the twelve (12) manufactured prototype sets, ten (10) will be deployed in the clinical studies foreseen in the project, while two (2) will be retained for laboratory testing, validation of upgrades and replacement of components if needed. This deliverable along the production of the prototypes, represent a key step towards the demonstration of the ThrombUS+ system in real-world conditions.

1. Introduction

The purpose of D4.6 is to create 12 prototypes of the ThrombUS+ wearable system, related to alternative monitoring and prevention methods included in the project. This document summarises the final design of the prototypes of the system, which will be used during clinical studies.

Starting from the modular subdivision of the ThrombUS+ system introduced in the deliverable D2.3¹, the deliverable D2.4² defined the system submodules and divided them into two wearables that can also be worn individually (**Error! Reference source not found.**):

The **Wearable Ultrasound Device** (WUSD) includes: the C-shell Semirigid Wearable (CSW), working with the Electronic Actuator Controller (EAC), the low profile ultrasound transducers, controlled by the ultraportable beamformer, and integrated in the C-shell Semirigid Wearable.

The **Wearable Sensors Network** (WSN) includes: the Wearable Thigh Cuff (WTC), working with Electronic Actuator Controller (EAC), the Wearable Tetrapolar Electrode working with Electrical Impedance Module controller, the Limb Activity Module (LAM) sensors working with their controller, and the Light Reflection Rheography (LRR) sensor.

Deliverable D4.6 focuses on the **Wearable Sensor Network** (WSN) final prototypes following the wearable design approach described in D4.4³, and the wearable component of the **Wearable Ultrasound Device**. Final prototypes of other components of Wearable Ultrasound Device (WUSD) are described in D3.6.

2. Wearable Sensors Network

This section presents the different prototypes that compose the Wearable Sensors Network, which can be combined to create possible configurations of the system, according to the different DVT monitoring and prevention methods.

Although a total of 10 complete ThrombUS+ systems was foreseen, the consortium agreed to increase the production in order to have 2 more complete systems for laboratory activities. Following initial testing, 10 complete systems will be distributed to hospitals for the clinical studies C1 and C2, while the remaining 2 complete sets will be retained by technical partners, to test and validate future upgrades and improvements, provide real-time troubleshooting to clinical partners and replace any malfunctioning component if needed.

Starting from prototypes produced in D4.4 and tested in D4.5, these final prototypes include:

- 12 Wearable Thigh Cuffs,
- 12 Wearable Tetrapolar Electrodes,
- 12 Electrical Impedance Controllers with software,
- 36 Limb Activity Sensors, comprising 12 complete sets,

¹ Marozas V, Kaldoudi E, Prinz T, Lukoševičius A, Jurkonis R, Eitminavičius R, Didaskalou S, Vehkaoja A, Ahola R, Slabov A, Jegelevičius D, Balling S, Moutafidou A, Daukantas S, Rapalis A. Technical and functional requirements, Deliverable 2.3, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 31 October 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13897671>

² Cesana J, Annunziata S, Moltani LA, Didaskalou S, Jurkonis R, Marozas V, Lukoševičius A, Schubert F, Balling S, Architectural design of the strap and sock wearable, Deliverable 2.4, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 31 December 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14352778>

³ Cesana J, Annunziata S, LA Moltani LA. Prototypes of wearable strap and sock with sensors (2 prototypes), Deliverable 4.4, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 05 May 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15310384>

- 12 sets of Limb Activity Straps (including thigh, calf and foot straps),
- 12 Limb Activity Controllers with software,
- 12 Light Reflection Sensors with software and,
- textiles with special pockets to place the light reflection sensors.

The Wearable Sensors Network, utilising the abovementioned prototypes can be used to perform:

- Operator-independent Venous Occlusion Plethysmography for DVT monitoring.
- Operator-Independent Light Reflection Rheography-Based Monitoring of DVT.
- Operator-Independent Serious Gaming for DVT prevention.

Details on materials used for wearable prototypes are gathered in **Error! Reference source not found.** Each wearable prototype produced for D4.6 is also numbered to ensure traceability, supporting the management of its use. **Error! Reference source not found.** shows an example of a label for each wearable prototype described in the document.

2.1. Electrical Impedance Module prototypes

The Electrical Impedance Module (EIM) has been developed by TAU, task leader for T4.1. Additional information about the impedance plethysmography sensors and other submodules of EIM can be found in D4.1⁴.

The overall setup of the EIM includes: the wearable tetrapolar electrodes (WTE), the electrical impedance module controller, attached to the WTE through alligator clips and a dedicated software developed to support testing and optimisation, as shown in Figure 1. The standard cuffs used in the image to perform during venous occlusion plethysmography (VOP) will be replaced by the wearable thigh cuffs (WTC) prototypes, described in section 2.2, once the integration of the ThrombUS+ system is completed. Each component of this module is described in the following sections.

Figure 1. Left: Electrical impedance module components are displayed; Right: indicative image during venous occlusion plethysmography measurement utilizing the electrical impedance module.

2.1.1. Wearable Tetrapolar Electrode

Wearable parts related to the electrical impedance module have been developed by ComfTech in collaboration with TAU. After the testing phase, prototypes of wearable tetrapolar electrodes (WTE) are produced using the silver-based textile electrode (alternative 1) and not the silver/inox-based electrode

⁴ Verho J, Ahola R, Maja S, Vehkaoja A. Sensors and processing software for electrical impedance plethysmography DVT detection, Deliverable 4.1, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 05 January 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14540486>

(alternative 2)⁵. According to test performed by TAU, the chosen alternative provided better performance for the intended use.

The design of the WTE remains the same as the D4.4 prototype: two semi-independent straps integrating two textile electrodes' stripes, linked by a vertical textile loop.

This design gives freedom to adjust the straps on the patient using Velcro and guides the healthcare personnel during the wearing procedure, keeping the distance between the straps fixed to the optimal measure. The loop is also designed to serve as a guide for positioning a third strap that includes the limb activity module (LAM) sensor and light reflection module (LRM) sensor. The WTE prototype placed on the leg is represented in Figure 2. The first couple of electrodes is placed just above the ankle, and the second couple is on the calf.

Figure 2. WTE prototype on the leg.

2.1.2. Electrical Impedance Module controller and software

Electrical impedance plethysmography (EIP) controller with computer software has been developed by TAU. The EIP controller has been designed to measure small physiological changes in blood volume during venous occlusion plethysmography (VOP) measurement, and it allows measuring electrical impedance up to 20 excitation frequencies simultaneously. For testing purposes, the device can be controlled via computer software written in the C# programming language. The graphical user interface (GUI) of this testing software fully supports EIP controller's functionality. The EIP controller and screen capture of the GUI are shown in Figure 3 and Figure 4, respectively. A more detailed description of the EIP controller with software is presented in deliverable D4.1⁶. The initial controller delivered in D4.1 has received minor improvements in battery life. The software has been developed and is continuously being developed to support integration into the overall ThrombUS+ system, where all the hardware will be controlled by the Central Hub & Intelligence Module (CHI).

⁵ Cesana J, Annunziata S, LA Moltani LA. Prototypes of wearable strap and sock with sensors (2 prototypes), Deliverable 4.4, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 05 May 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15310384>

⁶ Verho J, Ahola R, Maja S, Vehkaoja A. Sensors and processing software for electrical impedance plethysmography DVT detection, Deliverable 4.1, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 05 January 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14540486>

Figure 3. EIP controller prototype. (A) Device casing; (B) Device casing opened to reveal main components; (C) Assembled circuit board; and (D) A small plug-in module containing MAX30009 front-end.

Figure 4. Screen capture of the technical graphical user interface (GUI) during venous occlusion plethysmography measurement.

2.2. Wearable Thigh Cuff

Wearable Thigh Cuff (WTC) is a submodule of the Wearable Actuator Module (WAM), used in combination with Electronic Actuator Controller (EAC) and Electrical Impedance Module (EIM) to perform venous occlusion plethysmography (VOP). Additional information about WAM can be found in D3.3⁷.

The design of the WTC remains the same as that of the D4.4 prototype: Neoprene coupled with Polyamide strap with Velcro regulation, internally covered with rigid Polyurethane to stiffen the soft external material, and including the bladder provided by MEDIS (Figure 5).

⁷ R. Eitminavičius, R. Jurkonis, V. Marozas, S. Daukantas, A. Sakalauskas, A. Slabov, Precise Tissue Compression Actuator, Deliverable D3.3, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 04 January 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14540479>

Figure 5. The Wearable Thigh Cuff (WTC) on the right, and the integrated MEDIS bladder (280 x 117 mm) on the left.

The design ensures great adjustment to different thigh circumferences; the Velcro can be attached everywhere on the external part of the strap. This cuff covers up to 80 cm of leg circumference. The bladder is placed inside a soft textile pocket, allowing an easy insertion and removal procedure.

The same Electronic Actuator Controller developed in WP3 will work both with the WTC and CSW (Figure 6). More information on these components is included in the D3.3 report. The WTC prototype placed on the leg is represented in Figure 7, the strap is placed on the thigh just above the knee.

Figure 6. Two prototypes of the Wearable Thigh Cuff (WTC) and the Electronic Actuator Controller (EAC).

Figure 7. The Wearable Thigh Cuff (WTC) prototype on the leg.

2.3. Limb Activity Module

Limb Activity Module (LAM) has been developed by KTU, Task Leader for T4.3. Additional information about Limb Activity Sensors can be found in D4.3⁸. The overall setup of the Limb Activity Module includes: three LAM sensors, integrated into three wearable straps, and the LAM controller with a dedicated software developed to support testing and optimisation. Each component of this Module is described in the following sections (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Left: Limb Activity Module components. Middle; LAM sensors and Controller worn on the right leg and, left; respective visualisation of leg orientation utilising the testing software.

2.3.1. Limb Activity Module Straps

Wearable parts related to the Limb Activity Module (LAM) have been developed by ComfTech in collaboration with KTU. The design of the LAM wearable remains the same as the D4.4 prototype: three independent straps with Velcro for thigh, calf and foot, each with a specific fabric pocket for one LAM sensor. But in this final version, some improvements were made: the elastic band used as a slot for the sensor has been reinforced with Polyurethane film to avoid loosening due to repeated use, and the material of the strap has been replaced with a latex-free, softer textile (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Limb activity module strap material. Top: version as presented in deliverable D4.4. Bottom: final prototype version after refinements.

⁸ Jucevičius M, Marozas V, Daukantas S, Lukoševičius A. Sensors and processing software for lower limb activity pattern recognition (2 sets), Deliverable 4.3, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 05 January 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14540539>

The design of the final prototype is shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10. Final prototype of the LAM straps, showing both internal and external views.
From top: thigh strap, calf strap, foot strap.

The limb activity module (LAM) strap placed on the calf can also include the light reflection module (LRM) sensor using the specific pocket, as described in Section 2.4.1. LAM straps set prototypes placed on the left leg are represented in Figure 11.

Figure 11. Limb activity module straps prototype worn on the left leg.

2.3.2. Limb activity module controller, sensors and software

LAM controller presented in Figure 12 has two robust ODU MINI-SNAP 10-pin connectors for sensor cables (Figure 13), one dedicated to each leg, and can accommodate up to 5 LAM sensors on each leg. It has a screen showing operational, battery status and errors. Controller housing is 3D printed from bio-compatible Polylactic Acid (PLA) material. It has a removable battery and can also be charged via USB-C connector.

Figure 12. Final prototype of the limb activity module controller, showing both controller and removable battery.

Figure 13. Limb activity sensor cable. Controller connector (top) and sensor connector (bottom).

LAM sensors presented in Figure 14 include inertial measurement units (IMU) for activity and orientation sensing, temperature sensor for body and ambient temperature sensing and an auxiliary four-channel photoplethysmography sensor. The housing of the sensor is manufactured using stereolithography (SLA) 3D printing from biocompatible resin and tempered glass.

Figure 14. Final prototype of the limb activity module (LAM) sensor.

The entire LAM system in exploded view is presented in Figure 15.

Figure 15. Limb activity module in exploded view.

LAM software was developed in C# programming language and includes software development kit (SDK) that provides functions for simple integration into various ThrombUS+ subsystems, and a technical graphical user interface (GUI) for testing and development, which is presented in Figure 16. The 10 assembled Limb Activity Modules are shown in Annex 3.

Figure 16. Final prototype of the limb activity module (LAM) technical Graphical User Interface.

2.3.3. Improvements and updates of the limb activity module components

Compared to the initial prototypes produced within task T4.3 and presented in deliverable D4.3 the following improvements and updates were implemented in the final limb activity module component prototypes:

- Improvements on electronics hardware included corrections on PCB layout to pass Design for Manufacturability (DFM) review of the manufacturer.
- Improvements on mechanical design include a new battery lock mechanism, buttons' design, refined housing model quality and tolerances, as well as overall design update simplifying 3D printing and assembly for smoother and scalable production.
- Improvements on device firmware and software include updates on LVDS communication protocol implementation, reducing packet loss, wireless Wi-Fi credentials exchange (with the Central Hub & Intelligence Module) solution based on SoftAP (Software-enabled Access Point) method, improved settings exchange framework allowing CHI more flexible configuration of the sensors, added data logger functionality in the GUI.

2.4. Light Rheography Module

The Light Rheography Module (LRM) has been developed by MEDIS, and its components are presented in detail within D4.2. *Sensors and Processing Software for Light Reflection Rheography DVT Detection*⁹. Each component of this module is described in the following sections.

2.4.1. Light Rheography Module pocket

The wearable parts related to Light Rheography Module (LRM) have been developed by ComfTech in collaboration with MEDIS. The LRM module components remain the same as the D4.4 prototype: the LRM sensor is placed inside a separate pocket that can slide along an adjustable strap (Figure 17). This solution gives more freedom to place the LRM sensor according to the single patient, and the Velcro adjustment ensures good adherence to the skin.

Figure 17. LRR straps on the legs and test software.

The pocket is created by sewing a laser-cut disk of textile reinforced with PU film and a laser-cut disk of meshed textile, which does not interfere with the device measurements. On the back, the pocket has an

⁹ Balling S, Querengässer J, Schubert F, Sensors and processing software for light reflection rheography DVT detection, Deliverable 4.2, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 05 January 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14540537>

opening for an easy insertion and removal procedure for the LRM sensor and an elastic loop to guide the sliding on the strap.

Figure 18 shows the LRM sensor and its placement inside the pocket and on the strap.

Figure 18. LRM sensor front and back, and its placement inside the LRM pocket.

Due to the required position on the calf for both the LRM and LAM sensors, the LRM pocket will be placed on the LAM calf strap (Figure 19). An additional LRM calf strap is included for use on the other leg (Figure 20).

Figure 19. LAM calf strap, including LRM sensor pocket.

Figure 20. Additional LRM calf strap, including LRM sensor pocket.

To guide the wearing procedure, the LAM calf strap is made to pass inside the textile loop that joins the EIM straps, creating a three semi-independent straps wearable solution, already presented in D4.4.

2.4.2. Light Reflection Rheography sensor hardware

The sensor hardware consists of three main parts: the digital circuit, the analogue circuit and the power supply. The components are assembled on a single PCB (printed circuit board).

Digital Circuit: The digital circuit comprises an ESP32S3 microcontroller (μC) as its principal component. The microcontroller under discussion is notable for its powerful and flexible capabilities, thus positioning it as the leading device in its series. The microcontroller's primary functions encompass the regulation of the power supply, the provision of a "user interface" (by means of button state verification and the control of the RGB LED to communicate device status to the user), the management of the analogue circuit, and the control of power management.

Analog Circuit: The operation of the analogue circuit is controlled by the microcontroller that is part of the digital circuit. Its primary functions encompass the provision of the required current for the IR LED, amplification and analog to digital conversion to measure the intensity of the back scattered IR light, measurement of battery voltage and the provision of this information to the microcontroller (for power management).

Power Supply: The power supply comprises three components: the lithium polymer (LiPo) battery, the battery management integrated circuit, and the magnetic connector, which is used to connect a USB cable for the purpose of powering the battery.

2.4.3. Light Reflection Rheography software

The software can be categorised into two principal approaches: the "central software", which communicates with the device software using a wireless (WLAN) IP connection, and the device software, otherwise referred to as "firmware".

The central software is designed to facilitate the collection of information regarding available modules as LRM, and their respective device states. It is also capable of initiating LRR measurements by transmitting a designated start command and subsequently processing measurement results. As the central software is addressed in another work package, it will not be elaborated on further in this documentation. All subsequent sections will focus exclusively on the device software, or "firmware".

The primary operating functions of the device software are as follows:

- initialisation of all components (microcontroller and connected circuits) after reset,
- configuration and initialisation of the WLAN interface,
- storage of device settings, for example, the IP address,
- power management,
- provision of the user interface, which comprises a button and an RGB LED for user interaction and device state information,
- provide device state information to the central software,
- receive control commands from the central software, i.e., these may be issued in order to initiate an LRR measurement,
- the measurement results must be provided to the central software.

2.4.4. Sensor Case

The sensor case is employed for the secure placement and installation of the electronic hardware components. The decision to utilise in-house 3D printing was made to enhance flexibility, given the available resources. In the course of the case design process, multiple modifications and improvements were implemented to address all stages of further sensor development, optimised battery management,

and minimised size. As illustrated in Figure 18 on the left, a representation of the sensor case, both top and bottom, serves as a visual reference.

3. Wearable Ultrasound Device (WUSD)

This section presents the wearable prototype that works within the Wearable Ultrasound Device (WUSD). Other prototypes that are part of the same subsystem are presented in D3.6.

3.1. C-Shell type Semirigid Wearable

C-shell type Semirigid Wearable (CSW) is a submodule of the Wearable Actuator Module (WAM), used in combination with Electronic Actuator Controller (EAC), to achieve the Compression Duplex Ultrasonography (CDUS) method.

The design of this component has been revised and improved from D4.4 prototypes. The textile parts followed the new configuration of the 3D-printed shell. Unlike the previous version, the CSW now has only one 3D-printed shell, and the other part of the strap is only textile.

A comparison of the two designs is shown below: the D4.4 prototype is composed of two rigid 3D-printed shells covered with textile envelopes and a textile pocket for the bladder; the updated prototype is composed of one flexible 3D-printed shell laterally covered with textile and a textile pocket for the bladder.

Figure 21. D4.4 prototype of the C-shell type Semirigid Wearable (CSW).

Figure 22. D4.6 prototype of the C-shell type Semirigid Wearable (CSW).

The textile parts used to cover the 3D-printed shell are designed to be easy to insert and remove, facilitating cleaning procedures. They are connected using automatic buttons on the back of the shell. Velcro loops placed on these lateral parts are used to attach this component to the pocket bladder, which is covered with Velcro hooks.

Rigid and elastic materials are used in the different parts of the wearable to follow functional requirements. The result is a semirigid wearable strap that can be adjusted to fit the circumference of the thigh and keep the transducer in position during Compression Duplex Ultrasonography.

Figure 23. C-shell type Semirigid Wearable (CSW) prototype on the leg.

4. Conclusions and next steps

With all 12 replicates of the prototypes produced, KTU, responsible for system integration, will collect them to assemble and validate:

- 10 ThrombUS+ Wearable Sensors Network systems to be used in clinical studies C1 and C2,
- 2 ThrombUS+ Wearable Sensors Network systems that will serve as laboratory prototypes to implement, test and validate future improvements, upgrades and updates, and replace any malfunctioning system if required.

In addition to the prototypes, technical partners will prepare instruction documents to guide clinicians and operators in the use of the system. The instruction will cover the procedures for wearing and operating the wearable sensor network, as well as assembly and disassembly, cleaning and disinfection.

The delay in finalising and submitting deliverable D4.6 is mainly due to the additional time required for the production and validation of each component. In particular, the 3D printing process proved to be more time-consuming than initially anticipated when scaling up to a higher number of pieces, due to longer printing cycles, material availability constraints, and the need to evaluate alternative materials following the discontinuation of the originally selected one. Consequently, additional time was required for test printing and verification of the new material to ensure that the mechanical properties and skin-contact requirements were met before proceeding with producing all prototypes.